

Maximizing Learning in Caring for Older Patients Through a Multi-Specialty Simulation Approach

Mohamed Abbas [†] ,
Cathryn Buechel
*Nottingham University Hospitals NHS Trust; Derby Rd,
Nottingham NG7 2UH, United Kingdom*

[†] Co-First Author

Abstract

Background: Simulation-based learning has been utilized in medical education and studied to enhance its educational impact since the 1960s (Hallinger, & Wang, 2020). However, there is a lack of multispecialty simulations in the literature (Fisher, & Walker, 2014; Age UK. 2023; NHS England, 2021; Romero-Ortuno, Stuck, & Masud, 2022; Keijsers, et al., 2016). We developed and delivered simulations on Orthopaedics and Geriatric topics. Simulation mannequins, role players, imaging, and simulated clinical documentation were incorporated into scenarios. We evaluated the effectiveness of this approach on students' knowledge and confidence when caring for older patients.

Methods: Fourth-year medical students at the University of Nottingham received simulation-based teaching during their Geriatrics placement at Queens Medical Centre. Their knowledge and confidence levels were assessed before and after the simulations. We utilized six knowledge-based and six confidence-level questions mapped to their learning outcomes for hip fractures, pressure ulcers, and discharge planning stations. In addition, we asked students to provide scenario-specific feedback and their thoughts on whether the simulation workshop was pitched at the right level.

Results: Students' knowledge and confidence levels improved significantly following the simulation workshop. About 75% of the students displayed enhanced results in the knowledge-based category. In terms of their confidence level, there was improvement seen across all simulation stations, with most learners feeling four times more confident when comparing proportions pre and post-simulation. Furthermore, 99% of the students thought the simulations had positively impacted their learning.

Conclusion: Our findings demonstrate the effectiveness of the multispecialty simulation approach in undergraduate geriatrics teaching. Given significant improvements in students' knowledge, confidence levels, and positive feedback, we aim to continue delivering this multispecialty simulation-based teaching to our students. To measure the long-term efficacy of this approach, we can perhaps re-evaluate students learning after a month to assess the efficacy of this simulation workshop.

Keywords: *Simulation, Learning, Elderly, Recurrent Falls.*

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Introduction

Given an increase in the aging population in around the world, medical students and junior doctors are spending significant amount of time caring for older patients (Colombier, 2017; Dixon, et al., 2004). More specifically, elderly patients are at higher risk of suffering from falls, leading to sustaining injuries (Vass, et al., 2009). Management of falls in older populations requires a multi-speciality and multi-disciplinary approach (Falaschi, & Marsh, 2020). However, there is a lack of multi-specialty simulation-based teaching in the literature to prepare the doctors of tomorrow (Fisher, & Walker, 2014; Age UK. 2023; NHS England, 2021; Romero-Ortuno, Stuck, & Masud, 2022; Keijsers, et al., 2016).

We developed the proposed planning process to implement inter-professional education within a geriatric medicine department by C.J.P.W. Keijsers et al. (2016), (Figure 1) and delivered simulations on topics encompassing Orthopaedics and Geriatrics. Simulation mannequins, role players, imaging and simulated clinical documentation were incorporated into scenarios. We evaluated the effectiveness of this approach on students' knowledge and confidence when caring for older patients.

The widely accepted definition for inter-professional education is described by CAIPE (Centre for the Advancement of Interprofessional Education) as "Interprofessional education occurs where two or more health professionals learn with, from and about each other to improve collaborations and the quality of care" (CAIPE, 2011).

Figure 1. Proposed Planning Process for Implementation of Inter-Professional Education within a Geriatric Medicine department

Source: Keijsers et al. (2016)

The multidisciplinary approach of geriatric medicine is typified by the close collaboration of physicians, nurses, physiotherapists, occupational therapists, psychologists, pharmacists, and many other disciplines in what is known as a "collaborative practice" (WHO, 2010). A growing number of medical professionals are anticipated to have a role in providing care in the future due to the global trend of longer life expectancies, patient safety, and the complexity of patients' requirements (Colombier, 2017). This has resulted in a growing demand for suitable training in geriatric medical care through a multidisciplinary approach (Mezey, et al., 2008).

In traditional education, trainees in different disciplines are usually trained separately during undergraduate and/or postgraduate training. Currently, training in interdisciplinary teamwork for effective learning by collaborative practice, in this case interdisciplinary collaboration, has not received much attention from any profession (Mohammed, Anand, & Ummer, 2021). However, it is well known that communication and collaboration problems may cause team failure and negative patient outcomes (Zwarenstein, et al., 2013). A solitary discipline educational approach does increase each profession's knowledge and skills separately; however, there may also be advantages in interprofessional education (IPE), which is a growing phenomenon in medical education (Alnaami, et al., 2023). Furthermore, the WHO explained that IPE is an innovative and system-transforming solution that will ensure the appropriate supply, mix, and distribution of the health workforce (WHO, 2010; Mezey, et al., 2008; Lisk, 2013; Kvarnstrom, 2008; Kitto, et al., 2014).

Methods

Fourth-year medical students at the University of Nottingham received simulation-based teaching in their Geriatrics placement at Queens Medical Centre. Their knowledge and confidence level were assessed before and after the Simulations. We utilized six knowledge-level questions, and six confidence level-based questions mapped to learning outcomes for the Hip Fractures, Pressure ulcers, and Discharge planning stations. In addition, we asked students to provide scenario-specific feedback and their thoughts on whether the simulation workshop was pitched at the right level.

Results

Students' knowledge and confidence improved significantly after the simulation workshop. In the knowledge-based category, up to 75 % of the students showed improvement. In terms of their confidence level, there was improvement seen across all simulation stations with some students feeling up to four times more confident. Furthermore, 99 % of the students thought simulations made a positive impact in their learning. From figures 2-9 we noticed an overall improvement in knowledge and understanding of trainees to manage the falls and fractures in the elderly. Also, from Tables 1 and 2, there is an overall perception of satisfaction with the training the feel of the good impact, and the feeling that they have the confidence to learn more and manage such cases.

Figure 2. Perception of Medical Students and Feeling of Confidence Pre-Simulation and Improvement Post-Simulation

Figure 3. Perception of Medical Students and Feeling of Confidence Pre-Simulation and Improvement Post-Simulation

Figures 4. Perception of Medical Students and Feeling of Confidence Pre-Simulation and Improvement Post-Simulation

Figures 5. Perception of Medical Students and Feeling of Confidence Pre-Simulation and Improvement Post-Simulation

Figures 6. Perception of Medical Students and Feeling of Confidence Pre-Simulation and Improvement Post-Simulation

Figures 7. Perception of Medical Students and Feeling of Confidence Pre-Simulation and Improvement Post-Simulation

Figures 8. Perception of Medical Students and Feeling of Confidence Pre-Simulation and Improvement Post-Simulation

Figures 9. Perception of Medical Students and Feeling of Confidence Pre-Simulation and Improvement Post-Simulation

Tables 1. Perception of Trainees about the Training on Falls & Fragility Fractures, Bed Ulcer and Admission of patients

	Frequency	Percent
Total answers	186	100
Very good teacher and Scenario, Excellent station with all the teaching we needed to know	127	76.5
Good use of manikin and grading pathway, Excellent session, very useful but would appreciate more time	124	74.7

Table 2. Perception of the Workshop was Pitched at the Right Level of Your Learning? General Feedback

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	87	52.4	52.4
Just right	77	46.4	46.4
Too difficult	1	.6	.6
Too easy	1	.6	.6
Total	166	100.0	100.0

Discussion

There is so much interest in interprofessional education, and especially the impact of training considering the multispecialty approach is very successful in multiple studies as revealed by the review of literature and considering the adult learning theories of how to get our training into a higher retention of knowledge and the use of knowledge actual to change and improve practices dot.

Our findings are like the findings of other studies in which there is a brief that good preparation for the training of trainees and using adult learning theories will have a greater impact on the outcome of the training. Adding to this the multispecialty approach increases the communication and collaboration between different specialties which leads the two excellent outcomes in the context of patient care which is the goal of all of us as healthcare professionals.

Conclusion

Our findings demonstrate the effectiveness of the multi-specialty simulation approach in undergraduate geriatrics teaching. Given this vast improvement in students' knowledge and their confidence level together with positive feedback, we aim to continue delivering this multi-specialty simulation-based teaching to our students. To measure the long-term efficacy of this approach, we can perhaps re-evaluate students after a month to allow evaluation of learning over time.

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